

**MOTIVATION, IDENTITY, AND SENSE OF PURPOSE OF SELECTED
ST. DOMINIC COLLEGE OF ASIA GRADUATING HIGHER
EDUCATION STUDENTS: A BASIS ON THE DEVELOPMENT
OF THE DOMINICAN LIFE SUCCESS SCALE**

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Motivation, Identity, and Sense of Purpose of Selected St. Dominic College of Asia Graduating Higher Education Students: A Basis on the Development of the Dominican Life Success Scale

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess whether the sense of purpose and identity status of graduating higher education students at St. Dominic College of Asia affects their intrinsic motivation. Using a quantitative survey research design, respondents consisted of 200 selected graduating students from St. Dominic College of Asia. The Dominican Life Success Scale (DLSS), a 90-item scale constructed by the researchers and validated by subject-matter experts (SMEs) in the field of Psychology, was employed. The results showed that students who have a clear sense of purpose in their academic journey are highly motivated by personal growth and fulfillment, rather than external rewards. Those with a strong sense of personal identity also exhibit high levels of intrinsic motivation in their studies. Overall, having a clear purpose and strong identity significantly influence students' motivation and academic success in higher education.

Keywords: *sense of purpose, identity status, intrinsic motivation*

Introduction

In the area of higher education, understanding the motivation, identity, and sense of purpose among students is crucial for their overall success and well-being. Existing literature lacks a comprehensive exploration of the interaction between motivation, identity, and sense of purpose among higher education students and their academic performance. Recognizing this gap is essential for developing targeted interventions and support systems that cater to the unique needs of these students. Moreover, findings from this study would further expand upon existing research regarding the relationship and impact of factors such as motivation, sense of purpose, and identity status on the academic progress and success of students in higher education levels. A preliminary examination of the current status of motivation, identity, and sense of purpose among selected St. Dominic College of Asia higher education students are important. By doing so, this study introduces the Dominican Life Success Scale, an original tool designed to fill this void. By focusing on the specific dynamics of motivation, identity, and sense of purpose within this unique academic environment, the research endeavors to contribute valuable insights to the broader field of higher education studies. Aligned with St. Dominic College of Asia's vision to be a dynamic and proactive university, this study also focuses on enhancing student development by investigating motivation, identity, and sense of purpose. By examining how purpose, identity, and motivation impact academic performance and well-being, it aligns with the mission to innovate education and support comprehensive student growth. Moreover, this study also serves as a stepping stone towards further preparing more SDCA graduates who are productive, socially responsible, and competent. It promotes research and technology utilization through modern methodologies and evidence-based practices and addresses academic community concerns by offering guidance for educators to create supportive environments and targeted interventions, improving students' overall quality of life.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of sense of purpose among respondents?
2. What is the level of identity status among respondents?
3. What is the level of intrinsic motivation among respondents?
4. Is there a significant relationship among correlated factors?

Literature Review

Intrinsic Motivation

"Intrinsic motivation is defined as the doing of an activity for its inherent satisfactions rather than for some separable consequence," according to Ryan and Deci (2000, p. 56). It has to do with internal elements that a person develops via engagement in activities, such as interest, enjoyment, or challenge, for the delight or satisfaction ingrained in the activities. Moreover, extrinsic motivation was characterized as "a construct that pertains whenever an activity is done." in order to achieve a distinct result (Ryan & Deci, 2000, p. 60, As cited in Students' Motivation in Online Learning During COVID-19 Pandemic Era: A Case Study, 2020). Student achievement in Higher Education Institutions is driven by their level of academic intrinsic drive. Additionally, students who are genuinely motivated are more likely to feel more independent, overcome obstacles, and participate in academic activities like turning in assignments on time, attending class, and getting good test results. Furthermore, research indicates that mature students exhibit higher levels of intrinsic drive for learning than do typical traditional students (Shillingford & Karlin, 2013; Bye, Pushkar, & Conway, 2007, As Cited in Academic Intrinsic Motivation and Learning Engagement in Mature Students in Private Higher Education Institutions in the South of

England, 2022). Further empirical studies have shown that Positive psychosocial adjustment is linked to intrinsic motivation. For instance, pupils who are intrinsically motivated and ready to learn do better academically and exhibit greater academic tenacity than children who are not as intrinsically motivated. (Deci, Vallerand, Pelletier, & Ryan, 1991, As Cited in Academic Intrinsic Motivation and Learning Engagement in Mature Students in Private Higher Education Institutions in the South of England, 2022). Hence, this also indicates the crucial importance of intrinsic motivation in propelling students' academic success as they encounter daily challenges and decisions in their academic pursuits. An area of interest within the field of motivation research centers on academic motivation, defined by Mahato and Barman (2019) as the internal force that drives a student to complete a task. This aspect of study pertains to tasks, projects, assignments, and other academic activities designed to improve students' cognitive, emotional, and physical learning experiences.

Identity Status

One key factor influencing students' educational experiences, progress, and success is their academic identity. Academic identity is a component of students' overall self-concept that centers on how important academic attainment and performance are to them (Welch & Hodges, 1997). Academic identity was recently defined by Yukhymenko-Lescroart (2014) as the degree to which students regard their academic tasks and responsibilities as essential to their overall sense of self (As cited in High School Students' Subjective Well-being: The Role of Life Purpose and Academic Identity 2023). Research suggests that students who come to university focusing on gathering information are generally well-equipped to handle the academic, social, and personal hurdles they will encounter. These information-centric students demonstrated they have the necessary resources and mindset to manage their time effectively and conduct their lives responsibly and self-directed. They exhibited the most significant level of emotional independence, reflecting a strong self-awareness. Moreover, it is common for young adults to face complex and contradictory choices about their careers, relationships, ideologies, and life paths that can considerably drive them to the conflict stage of their identity development. However, there are ways to deal with the identity crisis in a late adolescent. On a behavioral level, they are intended to capture the essence of Erikson's notion. Identity statuses are defined by the existence or lack of inquiry and commitment in work, philosophy, and interpersonal values.

Sense of Purpose

According to Damon et al. (2003), purpose refers to a person's consistent, broad aim to accomplish a goal that enriches their life and advances causes greater than themselves. (As cited in Sense of Purpose and Progress Towards Degree in Freshman College Students, 2020). In fact, Leppel (2005) discovered that college persistence is higher among students who wish to pursue education for the sake of society rather than just for financial gain. (As cited in Sense of Purpose and Progress Towards Degree in Freshman College Students, 2020). A eudaimonic view of well-being that emphasizes the significance of leading a purposeful life in accordance with one's strongly held values and potential is conceptually linked to a sense of purpose in life (Waterman, 1993, As cited in High School Students' Subjective Well-being: The Role of Life Purpose and Academic Identity 2023). A study found that purpose awakening and humanitarian purpose indirectly improve first-year GPA, academic standing, and retention via degree commitment. Altruistic purpose also indirectly boosts first-year GPA via academic identity, underscoring the importance of purpose in college achievement (Yukhymenko-Lescroart & Sharma, 2020). Purpose and study engagement are critical markers of academic accomplishment and well-being (Dahl et al., 2020; Martínez et al., 2019; Widlund et al., 2018). The degree to which students have long-term goals and a sense of direction in life, or their sense of purpose, is positive and positively correlated with resilience and perseverance, positive self-image, life satisfaction, and other benefits such as the management of study habits (Bronk et al., 2019). Xerrie et al. (2018) also found that successful teacher-student interactions, excellent student-student relationships, and a strong sense of purpose for pursuing a higher education degree all positively impacted student participation in academic activities and perceptions of workload. Students with high-impact and social-impact attitudes outperformed others in terms of academic achievement. On the other hand, those with a low-impact attitude had fewer desirable characteristics in terms of purpose and academic engagement. Early assessment of a student's attitude based on their sense of purpose enables treatments to improve their well-being and academic progress. The findings suggest that educators can foster a shift towards self-transcendent motivations regarding students' overall sense of purpose to nurture their well-being and potentially boost their academic performance (Hudig et al., 2021). According to Sharma and de Alba (2018) and a study by Jongbloed and Andres (2015), participants' feeling of well-being included reaching their most important life objectives and further experiencing synchronization across several life domains because of a stronger sense of meaning and purpose in life (As cited in High School Students' Subjective Well-being: The Role of Life Purpose and Academic Identity 2023). Similarly, Sharma and de Alba's (2018) study demonstrated that students' general sense of happiness and well-being was enhanced and their motivation to achieve present and future goals was increased when they had a strong sense of purpose in life (As cited in High School Students' Subjective Well-being: The Role of Life Purpose and Academic Identity 2023).

Methodology

The study's research design is quantitative as it is more effective in identifying relationships among the study's variables. This research aims to investigate the interplay between identity formation, purpose, and intrinsic motivation among higher education students, primarily higher education graduating students at St. Dominic College of Asia. The primary focus is developing the Dominican Life Success Scale as the final output of this study to serve as a tool for measuring the current Intrinsic Motivation, Identity Status, and Sense of Purpose of the graduating higher education students of SDCA. The research utilizes structured questionnaires to gather

sufficient quantitative data. This deliberate focus on quantitative research facilitates the generation of numerical data, allowing for statistical analyses and a rigorous examination of the proposed relationships among the variables of interest. This research concentrates on graduating higher education students aged 21 and above, both regular and irregular, across diverse courses at St. Dominic College of Asia. Other demographic factors such as gender were excluded from the sample as Stolk et al. (2021) have reported subtle to no significant differences between male and female higher education students' level of intrinsic motivation. Hatano et al. (2022) have also found that while gender differences were found between the identity status formation of their college respondents, the differences were overall similar and identical. Similarly, the sense of purpose of college students in the study of Cebu (2023) was also reported to have no direct relationship with demographic variables such as age and gender. Employing a quantitative approach and the Dominican Life Success Scale, the study used purposive sampling to target graduating students.

The Dominican Life Success Scale (DLSS)

The goal of this study is to create and provide a new basis for the development of the Dominican Life Success Scale, which has been designed to determine the current Identity Status and Sense of Purpose of Higher Education Students of SDCA and how such factors affect their overall current Intrinsic Motivation towards their academic pursuits and successes. This psychological test uses a 7-point Likert scale to measure motivation levels based on the dimension of current identity status and a sense of purpose, creating survey items that reflect these constructs. Furthermore, in development of the Dominican Life Success Scale, the researchers created a table of criteria that reflect the aspects of motivation, sense of purpose, and identity status. The researchers ran many tests to ensure that the things were relevant. The test also underwent validation and reliability testing to ensure its psychometric soundness, reliability, validity, and usefulness so that it may be used in professional settings. Moreover, as the study aims to examine how factors such as identity status and sense of purpose influence one's level of intrinsic motivation, the utmost goal of the expected output is to put the results into application and to measure students' overall intrinsic levels of motivation based on identity status and sense of purpose as a guide and means of predicting their probability for success and achievement in their academic pursuits. Testing one's intrinsic motivation levels to determine the degree to which they are more likely to succeed in academics and future career goals. These further aid the educational and guidance system of the academic institution to establish more ways of promoting intrinsic motivation within students while also fostering their sense of purpose.

Procedure

The initial phase involves an in-depth review of the existing literature to refine the theoretical framework. This process encompasses a meticulous examination of recent studies and relevant theories pertaining to sense of purpose, identity status, and intrinsic motivation within the higher education context. The goal is to build a strong foundation for the subsequent phases of the research.

Following the enhancement of the theoretical framework, 75 items were meticulously developed for each factor—sense of purpose, identity status, and intrinsic motivation. These items are crafted to ensure clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness, aligning closely with the refined theoretical underpinnings.

The developed items undergo a stringent face and content validation process. Subject Matter Experts (SMEs) in the field evaluate the items for clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study's objectives. Feedback from experts is incorporated to refine and enhance the validity of the test. Upon validation, 75 items per factor were reduced to 40 items per factor, resulting in a total of 120 items for the test.

The validated questionnaire is distributed to the identified sample of Graduating Higher Education Students at St. Dominic College of Asia for Pilot Testing (50 students) through Google Forms. Informed consent was obtained from participants, and ethical considerations are carefully upheld throughout the distribution process. Strategies were employed to maximize response rates and ensure the representativeness of the data.

Responses collected from the online distributed questionnaires underwent a thorough quantitative statistical analysis by a statistician. This includes the computation of an appropriate Cronbach's alpha, reliability scoring, item analysis, and regression analysis to discern predictive relationships among sense of purpose, identity status, and intrinsic motivation. Predictive scores were derived, providing insights into the interplay of these factors.

Based on the results of the quantitative analysis and Cronbach's Alpha, the 40 items per factor were reduced to 30 items per factor to ensure that the statements with the highest reliability scores were kept and maintained within the DLSS. Resulting in a total of 90 items for the DLSS.

Upon final validation and item analysis of the test, the researchers underwent a final revision of the test for its official administration to 200 Higher Education Students in St. Dominic College of Asia, computed by Slovin's formula with 0.05% margin of error. After which, the researchers will be conducting data analysis and interpretation for the results of the data. This will serve the purpose of completing the thesis paper and as a compilation and interpretation of the effectiveness of the test developed.

The development of the DLSS Test manual, scoring sheet, answer sheet, and interpretation table. This table concisely outlines the significance of different score ranges for each factor, offering a practical guide for interpreting the study's findings. It serves as a valuable resource for educators, counselors, and policymakers in understanding and applying the research outcomes.

Data Analysis

The researchers utilized various data analysis methods by Microsoft Excel to further expand, organize, and make sense of the data gathered throughout the study into digestible, numerical values. Descriptive analysis in the form of finding the mean and standard deviation as the main snapshot of the test results' central tendency and variability were utilized to help summarize and describe the central features of the participants' levels of intrinsic motivation, sense of purpose and identity status. Inferential analysis was further determined to understand the implications of the data, explaining trends, patterns, and relationships that were observed in the results of the test. Moreover, predictive analysis through regression analysis was utilized by the researchers to accurately identify whether relationships between the 3 variables existed. It aids in understanding the impact of one or more independent variables on a dependent variable, mainly: the impact of one's sense of purpose and identity status to one's current intrinsic motivation. Consequently, hypothesis testing using the p-value was also done to determine whether the hypotheses were to be rejected or accepted. Most importantly, reliability testing with Cronbach's Alpha, a measure of internal consistency, was executed to determine how well the items in the test are stable and positively correlated to one another. Additionally, the test statements of the DLSS underwent careful and systematic analysis of Subject Matter Experts in the field of Psychology to ensure the validity of the test being developed.

Ethical Considerations

This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of St. Dominic College of Asia based on the compliance with the minimum standards of the SDCA Research Guidelines. Respondents were deployed based on their willingness to participate in this study with informed consent.

Results and Discussion

Level of Sense of Purpose

Table 1. Mean Distribution on the level of sense of purpose of the respondents

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. I find meaning in the challenges I encounter on my educational journey.	5.64	1.191	Agree
2. I find purpose in overcoming obstacles and challenges in my academic journey.	5.57	1.030	Agree
3. My academic achievements are meaningful to me because they align with my sense of purpose.	5.60	1.047	Agree
4. I frequently examine and revise my goals to ensure they are in line with my evolving sense of purpose.	5.59	1.043	Agree
5. I feel a strong sense of purpose in my academic pursuits.	5.38	1.145	Agree
6. I'm motivated by the idea that my contributions are part of something bigger than myself.	5.60	1.075	Agree
7. I feel that I have an active sense of control over my decisions in life.	5.54	1.160	Agree
8. I regularly reflect on how my education aligns with my short-term and long-term goals.	5.53	1.022	Agree
9. I have a clear understanding of what I want to achieve in life.	5.55	1.177	Agree
10. I frequently find meaning in the obstacles and hardships that I endure.	5.56	1.163	Agree
11. I feel a sense of urgency to fulfill my life's purpose.	5.61	1.051	Agree
12. I believe that I am in control of my own destiny.	5.55	1.151	Agree
13. I often take initiative in steering the direction in my life.	5.54	1.079	Agree
14. I believe my choices have a significant impact on my future.	5.76	.990	Agree
15. I find it easy to make decisions that are aligned with my personal values and goals.	5.59	1.029	Agree
16. I know that I have the power to set and achieve goals in my life.	5.66	1.058	Agree
17. Feeling a sense of freedom in my life is valuable to me.	5.78	1.000	Agree
18. I feel comfortable making decisions that are independent of other people's opinions.	5.55	1.168	Agree
19. I often try to incorporate my personal values into the choices I make everyday.	5.64	1.046	Agree

20. It is important for me to make decisions that reflect my authentic self.	5.70	.992	Agree
21. I know that I have the freedom to express my thoughts, even when they differ from the opinions of other people.	5.64	1.052	Agree
22. I feel that I have control over the path I choose to take in my life.	5.65	1.055	Agree
23. I do not easily conform to peer pressure during decision-making.	5.40	1.223	Agree
24. I often reflect upon the meaning behind my actions and decisions.	5.64	.977	Agree
25. I feel that I am proactive towards making my life meaningful and fulfilling.	5.56	1.059	Agree
26. I believe that I have the ability to adapt my goals to changing circumstances.	5.60	.997	Agree
27. I feel a sense of achievement when I am able to pursue the goals that align with my authentic self.	5.75	1.079	Agree
28. It gives me satisfaction whenever I am able to participate in activities that are aligned with my personal values.	5.63	1.009	Agree
29. It is important for me to seek out purpose in my everyday actions and decisions.	5.64	1.046	Agree
30. I feel that I have the capability to make meaningful plans about my future.	5.69	1.003	Agree
Grand Mean	5.6038	.79830	Agree

Students generally possess a high level of sense of purpose in their academic journey.

They find meaning in the challenges they encounter and view their academic achievements as meaningful.

Students are proactive in aligning their goals with their sense of purpose.

They exhibit high levels of motivation, self-control, reflection, goal clarity, and resilience.

Students are driven by intrinsic factors such as the desire for purposeful engagement.

They feel a sense of control over their decisions and prioritize personal growth over external rewards.

Students are proactive and intentional in their decision-making processes, guided by a strong sense of purpose.

They possess a strong sense of purpose and belief in personal control over their lives.

Students demonstrate initiative in steering the direction of their lives and believe their choices have a significant impact on their future.

They find it easy to make decisions that align with their personal values and goals.

Students value feeling a sense of freedom in their lives and prioritize decisions that reflect their authentic selves.

They are independent thinkers who do not easily conform to peer pressure.

Students engage in regular reflection on the meaning behind their actions and decisions.

They are proactive in seeking meaning and fulfillment in their lives.

Students exhibit a strong sense of adaptability, authenticity, value alignment, and future orientation.

Level of Identity Status

Table 2. Mean Distribution on the level of identity status of the respondents

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. My personal values play a significant role in shaping my identity.	5.96	.955	Agree
2. I am comfortable expressing my unique qualities and characteristics.	5.57	1.059	Agree
3. I have a clear understanding of my personal values and beliefs.	5.78	1.008	Agree
4. My identity is shaped by the diverse experiences I've had throughout my life.	5.73	.986	Agree

6. I actively seek to understand and appreciate different perspectives	5.82	.939	Agree
7. I actively pursue several career paths and life possibilities.	5.59	1.148	Agree
8. I have actively explored different academic subjects and career paths before committing to a specific field of study.	5.53	1.147	Agree
9. I am open to questioning and exploring my values and beliefs as part of my educational journey	5.76	.942	Agree
10. I often feel a sense of commitment and direction in my life decisions.	5.62	1.092	Agree
11. I think it is important to align my daily work with my long-term vocational goals.	5.72	.997	Agree
12. I consider myself to be deeply rooted into my ideological beliefs, even when faced with opposing viewpoints.	5.64	1.085	Agree
13. I find myself defending my ideological beliefs in discussions or debates because of my strong commitment to them.	5.59	1.038	Agree
14. I feel determined to overcome and persevere the challenges I encounter in my career path.	5.73	.970	Agree
15. I maintain my commitment and dedication despite criticism or setbacks in my career of choice.	5.71	1.026	Agree
16. I am no longer easily swayed by opinions of others to change my current career path.	5.56	1.101	Agree
17. I rarely experience doubt and uncertainty in my chosen career identity.	5.39	1.275	Agree
18. I believe that exploring various options for my career has helped me decide the best fitting vocational path for me.	5.63	1.009	Agree
19. I believe that the diversity of my experiences throughout my life has shaped the stability of my current identity today.	5.75	.923	Agree
20. My commitment to my ideology remains steadfast, even in the face of opposing viewpoints.	5.63	.974	Agree
21. I feel a strong sense of loyalty to my chosen career, even during challenging times.	5.71	1.011	Agree
22. I consider my vocational journey as a key component in my ongoing identity formation.	5.69	.985	Agree
23. I am open to adapting my vocational goals to align better with my evolving identity.	5.69	.910	Agree
24. I feel a strong sense of coherence between my vocational choices, ideology, and overall identity.	5.60	1.075	Agree
25. I actively seek to understand and appreciate different perspectives.	5.79	.909	Agree
26. I feel a sense of commitment and direction in my academic pursuits and long-term educational goals	5.61	1.046	Agree
27. I actively engage in exploring different aspects of my identity, such as cultural, academic, and personal values.	5.71	.975	Agree
28. In certain academic areas, I feel a strong sense of commitment, while in others, I am still in the process of exploration.	5.71	.938	Agree
29. I have faced pressure from peers, family, or educational institutions to conform to specific academic or career expectations.	5.73	1.036	Agree
30. I feel that I am strongly committed to my current vocation or career path.	5.63	1.029	Agree
Grand Mean	5.6763	.74570	Agree

Students highly value their personal values as significant contributors to shaping their identity.

They express comfort in showcasing their unique qualities and characteristics.

Students demonstrate a clear understanding of their personal values and beliefs.

They actively seek to understand and appreciate different perspectives.

Students are open to exploring multiple career paths and life possibilities.

They actively explore different academic subjects and career paths before committing to a specific field of study.

Students prioritize alignment between their daily work and long-term career goals.

They exhibit a strong sense of conviction in their ideological beliefs.

Students demonstrate determination and perseverance in their career paths.

They possess a strong sense of commitment and stability in their career and ideological identities.

Level of Intrinsic Motivation

Table 3.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. Overcoming academic challenges fuels my determination to succeed.	5.67	1.161	Agree
2. Personal growth in my academics serves as a strong driving force for me.	5.59	.983	Agree
3. The pursuit of knowledge is a primary motivator in my education.	5.62	1.059	Agree
4. I find joy and fulfillment in the process of learning and discovery.	5.58	1.053	Agree
5. Setting and achieving milestones keeps me inspired and driven.	5.61	1.128	Agree
6. I am motivated to make meaningful contributions to my chosen field of study.	5.51	1.103	Agree
7. I feel a sense of responsibility to my future self, driving my motivation.	5.75	1.063	Agree
8. I am motivated by a desire to create positive change through my education.	5.60	.998	Agree
9. It is easy for me to feel engaged while learning new concepts in my classes.	5.45	1.040	Agree
10. I tend to set academic goals that go beyond the minimum learning requirements.	5.43	1.096	Agree
11. I am not pressured by other people to do well in my studies.	5.10	1.473	Agree
12. I work hard for my studies because I want to.	5.56	1.137	Agree
13. I invested a lot of time and energy into my studies.	5.40	1.182	Agree
14. I believe that expanding my knowledge is important for my personal growth.	5.66	1.141	Agree
15. I am motivated by my personal values to do well in my classes/course.	5.57	1.049	Agree
16. I believe that I am responsible for the grades that I receive in my classes.	5.61	1.155	Agree
17. I am driven by a personal sense of achievement instead of just aiming for high grades in my academic work.	5.64	.997	Agree
18. I consider myself a value-driven individual.	5.51	1.080	Agree
19. I feel satisfied after doing my best efforts in class even when there is no immediate reward or recognition.	5.57	1.226	Agree
20. I am more likely to persist in challenging tasks because I enjoy the learning process.	5.50	1.094	Agree
21. My participation in school activities is driven by my genuine passion for learning instead of external pressures.	5.39	1.151	Agree
22. Personal growth is more important to me than external rewards.	5.57	1.132	Agree
23. I make decisions based on my personal values and interests rather than conforming to social norms.	5.50	1.165	Agree
24. I prioritize my own passions in life over conforming to societal expectations in my academic pursuits.	5.48	1.203	Agree
25. I find joy in engaging in activities purely for the pleasure they bring.	5.49	1.089	Agree
26. The satisfaction I gain from an activity is frequently enough to keep me going, even in the face of adversity.	5.48	1.075	Agree
27. I am driven to explore and understand topics that personally interest me.	5.69	1.105	Agree

28. Exploring new ideas and concepts is intrinsically satisfying for me.	5.70	1.102	Agree
29. I am motivated by a sense of personal accomplishment, even if the activity is not externally rewarded.	5.50	1.152	Agree
30. I am more likely to participate in activities that are related to my personal interests.	5.71	1.179	Agree
Grand Mean	5.548	.82256	Agree
	0		

Students are highly motivated by challenges, viewing them as opportunities for growth and success.

They are intrinsically motivated by the prospect of personal growth in academics.

Students are driven by a thirst for knowledge and intellectual curiosity.

They derive joy and fulfillment from the process of learning and discovery.

Students feel a sense of responsibility to their future selves, driving their motivation.

They are motivated by a desire to create positive change through their education.

Students find learning engaging and stimulating.

They tend to set academic goals that go beyond the minimum requirements.

Students invest a lot of time and energy into their studies.

They prioritize personal growth and value-driven decision-making in their academic pursuits.

Correlation with the Students’ Level of Intrinsic Motivation towards their Academic Pursuits and Endeavors according to Identity Status and Sense of Purpose of Higher Education Students

Table 4. Relationship with the students’ level of intrinsic motivation towards their academic pursuits and endeavors according to identity status and sense of purpose of higher education students

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
(Constant)	.631	.285	2.216	.028	Significant	Reject Ho
Level of Sense of Purpose	.469	.079	5.924	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Level of Identity Status	.403	.085	4.758	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

R squared: .613

Adjusted R squared: .609

Regression analysis shows a significant positive relationship between students' intrinsic motivation and their sense of purpose (coefficient = .469, $p < .001$).

Students who perceive a clear purpose in their academic pursuits tend to be more intrinsically motivated, supporting previous research linking purpose with motivation and academic success.

There is also a significant positive relationship between students' intrinsic motivation and their identity status (coefficient = .403, $p < .001$).

Students with a stronger sense of identity are more intrinsically motivated in their academic pursuits, aligning with Erikson's theory of identity development.

The model explains a substantial portion of the variance in students' intrinsic motivation (R squared = .613), highlighting the importance of sense of purpose and identity status in understanding and promoting motivation in higher education.

Level of Sense of Purpose

High levels of SP in the results of the final testing indicate that the graduating students of SDCA possess a strong sense of purpose and belief in personal control over their lives. Results report that they find meaning in the challenges they encounter and view their academic achievements as meaningful, indicating a resilience mindset that is associated with greater well-being and success. They exhibit high levels of motivation, self-control, reflection, goal clarity, and resilience. This aligns with self-determination theory, which suggests that individuals are driven by intrinsic factors such as the desire for purposeful engagement (Bandhu et al., 2024). Results also indicate that they find it easy to make decisions that align with their personal values and goals, including feeling a sense of freedom in their lives and prioritize decisions that reflect their authentic selves, suggesting a proactive approach to finding meaning in their lives, which is linked to higher levels of well-being (Siebert et al., 2020). They are independent thinkers who do not easily conform to peer pressure, engage in regular reflection on the meaning behind their actions and decisions, and are proactive in aligning their goals with their sense

of purpose. This finding is consistent with research by Steger et al. (2021), who argued that individuals with a strong sense of purpose tend to set clear goals that are meaningful and relevant to their overall sense of purpose.

Level of Identity Status

High levels of students' IS indicates that they highly value their personal values as significant contributors to shaping their identity. They express comfort in showcasing their unique qualities and demonstrate a clear understanding of their personal beliefs. This self-understanding lays a solid foundation for their identity development, enabling them to navigate life's complexities with a strong sense of purpose and direction (Darling-Hammond et al., 2019). They actively seek to understand and appreciate different life possibilities as they actively explore various academic subjects and career paths before committing to a specific field of study.

This exploratory mindset is valuable for discovering personal interests and passions, which can lead to more satisfying career choices (Abe & Chikoko, 2020). Results also indicate that they prioritize alignment between their daily work and long-term career goals as they demonstrate determination and perseverance. They possess a strong sense of commitment and stability in their career and ideological identities. This perspective aligns with theories of career development, which posit that career choices are intertwined with identity and play a crucial role in shaping one's sense of self (Jhangiani & Tarry, 2022).

Level of Intrinsic Motivation

Final results depict high levels of IM that indicate students prioritize personal growth and value-driven decision-making in their academic pursuits that is crucial for sustaining long-term engagement and commitment to academic pursuits (Wang et al., 2024). They are driven by a thirst for knowledge and intellectual curiosity, and derive fulfillment from the process of learning and discovery. Students feel a sense of responsibility to their future selves, driving their motivation. They tend to set academic goals that go beyond the minimum requirements, thus, invest a lot of time and energy into their studies. Such indicates that students are motivated to set ambitious goals for themselves, which is associated with higher levels of academic achievement (Steinmayr et al., 2019). They are highly motivated by challenges, viewing them as opportunities for growth and success, indicating a deep-seated motivation rooted in the satisfaction derived from personal achievement, aligning with self-determination theory (Bandhu et al., 2024), which emphasizes intrinsic motivation as a key driver for sustained engagement and performance in academic settings.

Relationship with the Students' Level of Intrinsic Motivation towards their Academic Pursuits and Endeavors according to Identity Status and Sense of Purpose of Higher Education Students

Regression analysis shows a significant positive relationship between students' intrinsic motivation and their sense of purpose (coefficient = .469, $p < .001$). Students who perceive a clear purpose in their academic pursuits tend to be more intrinsically motivated, supporting previous research linking purpose with motivation and academic success (Karlen et al., 2019). There is also a significant positive relationship between students' intrinsic motivation and their identity status (coefficient = .403, $p < .001$). Students with a stronger sense of identity are more intrinsically motivated in their academic pursuits, aligning with Erikson's theory of identity development. The model explains a substantial portion of the variance in students' intrinsic motivation ($R^2 = .613$), highlighting the importance of sense of purpose and identity status in understanding and promoting motivation in higher education.

Conclusions

Overall, the study's findings underscore the interconnected nature of intrinsic motivation, sense of purpose, and identity status among higher education students, highlighting their significance in shaping academic experiences and outcomes. The positive relationship between sense of purpose and intrinsic motivation suggests that students who perceive a clear direction and meaning in their academic pursuits are more likely to be driven by internal rewards, such as personal growth and fulfillment. This aligns with previous research emphasizing the role of purpose in enhancing motivation and academic performance. Additionally, the association between identity status and intrinsic motivation underscores the importance of a strong sense of self and values in driving students' engagement and perseverance in their academic endeavors. These findings collectively suggest that educators and institutions can enhance students' academic experiences by fostering a sense of purpose and identity, which, in turn, can lead to greater motivation, resilience, and overall well-being.

References

- Abe, E. N., & Chikoko, V. (2020). Exploring the factors that influence the career decision of STEM students at a university in South Africa. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7, 1-14.
- Alonso, R. K., Vélez, A., Martínez-Monteaudo, M. C., & Rico-González, M. (2023). Flipped Learning in Higher Education for the Development of Intrinsic Motivation: A Systematic Review. *Education Sciences*, 13(12), 1226. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13121226>
- Asif, S., Kamal, A., Fahim, M., Naveen, N., & Yousaf, F. (2018). Exploring Gender Differences in Academic Motivation among Adolescents. *Ophthalmology Update*, 16(4), 918-922.
- Bandhu, D., Mohan, M. M., Nittala, N. A. P., Jadhav, P., Bhadauria, A., & Saxena, K. K. (2024). Theories of motivation: A

- comprehensive analysis of human behavior drivers. *Acta Psychologica*, 244, 104177.
- Beboso, C. G. T., & Bual, J. M. (2022). Students' motivation and perception in learning social science using distance learning modality during COVID-19-pandemic.
- Cai, J., & Lian, R. (2022). Social support and a sense of purpose: The role of personal growth initiative and academic self-efficacy. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 788841.
- Cebu, J. (2023). Self-Efficacy of Filipino College Students as Correlates to Demographics. *United International Journal for Keesreho Technology*.
- Darling-Hammond, K. (2019). Queeruptions and the question of QTPOC thriving in schools-An excavation. *Equity & Excellence in Education*, 52(4), 424-434.
- Destin, M., & Williams, J. L. (2020). The connection between student identities and outcomes related to academic persistence. *Annual Review of Developmental Psychology*, 2, 437-460.
- Gustiani, S. (2020). STUDENTS' MOTIVATION IN ONLINE LEARNING DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC ERA: A CASE STUDY. *Holistics (Hospitality and Linguistics): Jurnal Ilmiah Bahasa Inggris*, 12(2).
- Hatano, K., Hihara, S., Sugimura, K., & Mizokami, S. (2023). Identity formation with gender differences in University students: a three-wave longitudinal study. *Current Psychology*, 42(34), 30174-30186.
- Hudig, J., Scheepers, A. W., Schippers, M. C., & Smeets, G. (2021). Motives for studying and student wellbeing: Validation of the motivational mindset model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 753987. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.753987>
- Hudig, J., Scheepers, A. W., Schippers, M. C., & Smeets, G. (2023). Motivational mindsets, mindset churn and academic performance: The role of a goal-setting intervention and purpose in life. *Current Psychology*, 42(27), 23349-23368. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-03462-8>
- Javed, R., Qureshi, F. H., & Khawaja, S. (2022). Academic intrinsic motivation and learning engagement in mature students in private higher education institutions in the South of England. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 9(2). DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v9i2.4131>
- Jhangiani, R., & Tarry, H. (2022). 3.1 The Cognitive Self: The Self-Concept. *Principles of Social Psychology-1st International H5P Edition*.
- Karlen, Y., Suter, F., Hirt, C., & Merki, K. M. (2019). The role of implicit theories in students' grit, achievement goals, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, and achievement in the context of a long-term challenging task. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 74, 101757.
- Kim, E. S., Chen, Y., Nakamura, J. S., Ryff, C. D., & VanderWeele, T. J. (2022). Sense of purpose in life and subsequent physical, behavioral, and psychosocial health: An outcome-wide approach. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 36(1), 137-147. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08901171211038545>
- Liu, C., Shi, Y., & Wang, Y. (2022, July). Self-determination theory in education: The relationship between motivation and academic performance of primary school, high school, and college students. In *2022 3rd International Conference on Mental Health, Education and Human Development (MHEHD 2022)* (pp. 923-929). Atlantis Press.
- Marcia, J. E., Waterman, A. S., Matteson, D. R., Archer, S. L., Orlofsky, J. L., Marcia, J. E., & Archer, S. L. (1993). Identity status in late adolescents: Scoring criteria. *Ego identity: A handbook for psychosocial research*, 205-240.
- Meens, E. E., Bakx, A. W., Klimstra, T. A., & Denissen, J. J. (2018). The association of identity and motivation with students' academic achievement in higher education. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 64, 54-70.
- Morris, L. S., Grehl, M. M., Rutter, S. B., Mehta, M., & Westwater, M. L. (2022). On what motivates us: A detailed review of intrinsic v. extrinsic motivation. *Psychological medicine*, 52(10), 1801-1816. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291722001611>
- Pfund, G. N., Bono, T. J., & Hill, P. L. (2020). A higher goal during higher education: The power of purpose in life during university. *Translational Issues in Psychological Science*, 6(2), 97.
- Siebert, J. U., Kunz, R. E., & Rolf, P. (2020). Effects of proactive decision making on life satisfaction. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 280(3), 1171-1187.
- Steger, M. F., O'Donnell, M. B., & Morse, J. L. (2021). Helping students find their way to meaning: meaning and purpose in education. In *The palgrave handbook of positive education* (pp. 551-579). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Steinmayr, R., Weidinger, A. F., Schwinger, M., & Spinath, B. (2019). The importance of students' motivation for their academic achievement—replicating and extending previous findings. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 464340.

Stolk, J. D., Gross, M. D., & Zastavker, Y. V. (2021). Motivation, pedagogy, and gender: Examining the multifaceted and dynamic situational responses of women and men in college STEM courses. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 8(1), 35.

Van der Kooij, K., in 't Veld, L., & Hennink, T. (2021). Motivation as a function of success frequency.

Motivation and Emotion, 45, 759-768. <https://doi.org/10.1007%2Fs11031-021-09904-3>

Wang, X. C., Zhang, M., & Wang, J. X. (2024). The Effect of University Students' Academic Self-Efficacy on Academic Burnout: The Chain Mediating Role of Intrinsic Motivation and Learning Engagement. *Journal of Psychoeducational Assessment*, 07342829241252863.

Xerri, M. J., Radford, K., & Shacklock, K. (2018). Student engagement in academic activities: a social support perspective. *Higher education*, 75, 589-605. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-017-0162-9>

Yukhymenko-Lescroart, M. A., & Sharma, G. (2023). Sense of purpose and progress towards Degree in freshman college students. *Journal of College Student Retention: Research, Theory & Practice*, 25(1), 187-207. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1521025120975134>

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